

Physico-chemical Estimation, a Possible Replacement of Bioassay in the Case of Gonadotropins

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A physico-chemical method has been suggested by allowing the hormone (chorionic gonadotropin) to react with *m*-xylohydroquinone and spectrophotometrically noting the optical density of the complex formed. This method appears to be more suitable for quantitative estimation than the biological methods involving uncertainties and inherent complexities.

The international standard of chorionic gonadotropin has been prepared from a mixture of six preparations and 0.1 mg. of this standard represents the international unit. Similarly in the case of pregnant mare's serum, the international unit is represented by the gonadotropic activity of 0.25 mg. of the standard. In actual practice, immature rats or mice are treated with variable doses and the activity is measured by the increase in weight of ovary and uterus, some histological changes in the uterus and vagina, increase in the weights of seminal vesicle, prostate, etc. Responses due to such stimulation are quite variable and necessarily a large number of animals are required for the statistical evaluation (of the results) which is always imperative in such cases.

Moreover, the bioassay, as the previous method is called, is also often confused. On the one hand, each preparation contains more than one type of gonadotropin in which the measurement of the constituents is difficult and, on the other, the responses of the target organs are also variable. End results in many cases are interdependent. As for example, the stimulation of the ovary, initially brought about by the follicle-stimulating hormone, is later augmented by the interstitial cell-stimulating hormone.

For this reason a physico-chemical method of estimation, if possible, would be more profitable as such a method is free from the uncertainties and complexities inherent in the bioassay, as mentioned above, and would be more quantitative.

In our previous studies¹, it has been observed that chorionic gonadotropin reacts with *m*-xylohydroquinone, as evidenced by the fact that the peak of the optical density in the spectrophotometric studies due to the latter (at 290m μ) disappears gradually when kept in contact with the chorionic gonadotropins and a new peak, probably due to the interaction of the two and formation of a complex, appears at 260m μ . The latter increases in height with time as the reaction proceeds to a certain limit, depending on the amounts of gonadotropin and hydroquinone used. If, however, the concentration of *m*-xylohydroquinone is kept constant, the change in the height of the peak, or the optical density, will be proportional to the concentration of gonadotropin. Thus a quantitative estimation appears probable and the present communication aims at this direction.

1. Sanyal and Ganguly, *Science & Culture*, 1954, 19, 356.
2. Thayer, "Vitamins and Hormones", 1946, Part 4, p. 211.

EXPERIMENTAL

Aqueous solutions of chorionic gonadotropin were prepared with deoxygenated water from ampoules of pregnyl containing 1000 international units. This was dissolved in 10 ml of water which served as the stock solution. Different amounts of this solution were diluted to 25 ml to prepare solutions of different concentrations.

A standard solution of *m*-xylohydroquinone was prepared with deoxygenated water.

Units of hormone in 25 ml sol.

FIG. 1

Solutions of hormone at different concentrations were mixed with those of hydroquinone such that the concentration of the latter in all cases was $1 \times 10^{-4} M$. Optical densities for each mixture were determined at 260 mμ after different intervals of time. The study was continued for 3 hr. when the peak was observed to rise to its maximum value. These maximum optical densities were then plotted against the concentration of the hormone in the mixture. The graph was linear up to 150 units of hormone in the mixture, but beyond this the linearity was not maintained.

As the above study was time-consuming and tedious, in another series, optical densities were determined after 15 minutes of mixing when the major portion of the reaction appeared to be complete and the peak attained an appreciable height. By plotting these optical densities against the concentrations of hormone, the graph was found linear even when there were 200 units of hormone in the mixture. This procedure appeared to be more convenient. Results are recorded in Table I and Fig. 1 and 2.

TABLE I

m-Xylohydroquinone = $1 \times 10^{-4} M$.

After 3 hours.		After 15 min.	
Units of hormone. (Fig. 1)	O.D. at 260 mμ.	Units of hormone. (Fig. 2)	O.D. at 260 mμ.
50 (i.v.)	0.76	50 (i.v.)	0.54
75 "	0.98	100 "	0.63
100 "	1.22	125 "	0.68
125 "	1.46	150 "	0.73
150 "	1.70	200 "	0.83
200 "	1.98	400 "	0.83
400 "	2.00		

In 25 ml solution.

DISCUSSION

From the experimental studies it was observed that while the *m*-xylohydroquinone concentration was constant, the absorption density of the complex at 260mμ increased with the concentration of the chorionic gonadotropin. This increase was linear up to a certain limit. This quantitative determination was more accurate and reliable. Units have been used in this case in preference to the molarity of the hormone because of the

reported variability and uncertainty of the molecular weights of the gonadotropins (from 30,000 to 100,000). It was also observed that samples varied in quality in the case of different trade marks. In one case 500-unit ampoules contained much greater quantity than in another sample of different trade mark, representing 1000 units per vial. It was also observed (not shown here) that it varied in samples of different trade marks although representing the same number of units. This is quite possible because of the uncertainties inherent in the bioassay.

FIG. 2

Principles governing the bioassay method consist of (I) a qualitative study of the active principle to determine the effect on the animal tissue and to develop procedures having the greatest quantitative reliability. In the bioassay (II) the second principle (*i. e.* reliable quantitative method) has not yet been achieved. Only an approximate estimation has been possible and that even after treating a large number of animals and applying elaborate statistical calculation (Thayer). The present method described herein appears to be adequately accurate, simple, and quick. It is quantitative of course, provided that there is proper response in the animal tissue in the qualitative study.

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